

Supplementary Information

Assessing benefits and costs of expanded green hydrogen production to facilitate fossil fuel exit in a net-zero transition

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Table of Contents:

List of Figures	3
List of Tables	4
S-1. Nomenclature	5
S-2. Data inputs for simulating wind turbine performance.....	8
S-3. Model schematics	11
S-4. Total number of offshore wind turbines	13
S-5. Completion years for each scenario	14
S-6. Wind speed data	15
S-7. Array power output	16
S-8. Annual project growth rates	19
S-9. Electrolyzers	20
S-10. Estimating avoided emissions	22
S-11. Reporting upper and lower bounds.....	25
S-12. Cost estimation	26
S-13. Retirements and replacement	30
S-14. Hydrogen storage	31
S-15. Uncertainty analysis.....	33
S-16. Monthly capacity factors	36
S-17. Natural gas consumption in the Maritimes	37

S-18. Natural gas pipeline	38
S-19. Results from the case with 5 starting turbines	39
S-20. Scenario δ – Transportation calculations	40

List of Figures

Figure S1. Schematics outlining how the recursive simulation proceeds in the scenarios under investigation.....	12
Figure S2. Scenario α cumulative distributions of the A) total real cost of the project, B) hydrogen production costs in 2025 (the initial year in the simulation), and C) hydrogen production costs at project completion.	33
Figure S3. Scenario β_{tot} cumulative distributions of the A) total real cost of the project, B) hydrogen production costs in 2025 (the initial year in the simulation), and C) hydrogen production costs at project completion.	34
Figure S4. Scenario β_{ind} cumulative distributions of the A) total real cost of the project, B) hydrogen production costs in 2025 (the initial year in the simulation), and C) hydrogen production costs at project completion.	34
Figure S5. Scenario γ cumulative distributions of the A) total real cost of the project, B) electric power production costs in 2025 (the initial year in the simulation), and C) the electric power production costs at project completion.	35
Figure S6. Scenario δ cumulative distributions of the A) total real cost of the project, B) hydrogen production costs in 2025 (the initial year in the simulation), and C) hydrogen production costs at project completion.	35
Figure S7 - Histogram of international routes split into 1000 km bins	42

List of Tables

Table S1. List of variables and their values	5
Table S2. List of variables used in the model for simulating wind turbine performance.....	8
Table S3. Model runs represent a range of deployment ambition and technical performance.....	9
Table S4. Five scenarios are investigated in this research effort.....	11
Table S5. Range of completion dates for each scenario, including in the cases that begin with 5 starting turbines rather than just 1 starting turbine.....	14
Table S6. Summary of upper and lower bound scenarios for which results are reported in the manuscript	25
Table S7. Nine costs are considered in this techno-economic analysis	26
Table S8. Cost estimates used in this analysis	27
Table S9. Storage size requirements for each scenario.....	31
Table S10. Cost ranges for hydrogen production scenarios with 5 starting turbines	39
Table S11. Cost ranges for scenario γ with 5 starting turbines	39
Table S12. Locations selected to replace “provincially labeled” Canadian locations	40
Table S13. Routes selected to replace specific Canadian domestic routes.....	41
Table S14. United States locations based on distance	43
Table S15. Routes selected to replace specific international routes	43

S-1. Nomenclature

Table S1. List of variables and their values

Variable	Description	Unit
A	Area swept by blades	m^2
$C_{CO_2}^{avoidance}$	Cost of CO ₂ avoidance (schematic)	USD
$C_{CO_2}^{social}$	Social cost of CO ₂ (schematic)	USD
C_E^{capex}	Electrolyzer CAPEX (schematic)	USD
C_E^{opex}	Electrolyzer OPEX (schematic)	USD
C_{Total}	Total cost at project completion (schematic)	USD
C_T^{capex}	Turbine CAPEX (schematic)	USD
C_T^{opex}	Turbine OPEX (schematic)	USD
C_{LCOH}	Levelized costs of hydrogen (schematic)	USD
C_{in}	Cut-in speed	m/s
C_{out}	Cut-out speed	m/s
C_p	Power coefficient	
CF_e	Electrolyzer capacity factor	%
CF_t	Turbine capacity factor	%
$D_{elec, fossil} (2050)$	Electric power generated by fossil resources in the Maritimes in 2050	GWh
D_{H_2}	H ₂ demand	m^3
$D_{H_2, ind}$	Industrial H ₂ demand	m^3
D_{supp}	Diesel supplanted by hydrogen	m^3
D_y	Distance traveled in the Maritimes each year (y)	km
d_m	Number of days in a month (m)	
$E_{CO_2}^{avoided}$	CO ₂ emissions avoided	kg
EF_s	Emission factor per emitting source (s)	gCO ₂ /kg, gCO ₂ /m ³ , gCO ₂ /L
$Elec_s$	Annual electricity production per emitting source (s)	GWh
EM_s	Annual emissions per emitting source (s)	kg
EM_s^{total}	Annual emissions of all sources (s)	kg
$EN_{i,m}$	Number of electrolyzers for each month (m) and year (i)	
G	Annual project growth rate	%

Variable	Description	Unit
H_{Supp}	Amount of hydrogen to supplant diesel transportation	m^3
h_{hub}	Hub height	m
HC_s	Heat content per emitting source (s)	GJ/t, GJ/ML, GJ/L
HR_s	Heat rate per emitting source (s)	Btu/kWh
i	Year	
i_{start}	Start year	
L	Annual reduction in cost (schematic)	USD
L_{array}	Array losses	%
L_{aux}	Auxiliary loads	%
L_s	Total summer climate losses	GWh / (Installed MW)
L_w	Total winter climate losses	GWh / (Installed MW)
MP_r	% of distance driven in Maritimes per route (r)	%
MD_r	Distance driven in Maritimes per route (r)	km
m	Month	
NG_{supp}	Natural gas supplanted by hydrogen in m^3	m^3
$NS_{r,y}$	# of shipments for each route (r) in each year (y)	
p_{air}^{hub}	Air pressure at hub	Pa
P_{elec}	Average daily array power output (schematic)	GWh
p_{elec}^{annual}	Annual electrical production by the turbine array	Wh
P_{elec}^{array}	Average daily net array electrical production	Wh
P_{elec}^{net}	Average daily net turbine electrical production	Wh
P_{elec}^{raw}	Average daily turbine raw electrical production	Wh
P_{H_2}	Average daily hydrogen output (schematic)	m^3
$P_{H_2}^{kg}$	Average daily hydrogen production	kg
$P_{H_2}^{m^3}$	Average daily hydrogen output	m^3
R	Blade radius	m
s	Fossil-fuel based emitting sources for scenario γ	
TD_r	Total distance traveled in each route (r)	km
TN_i	Number of turbines for each iteration year (i)	

Variable	Description	Unit
$TN_i(i = 1)$	Number of starting turbines at the beginning of simulation	
TN_{max}	Max number of turbines (specific to each scenario)	
T_{air}^{hub}	Air temp at hub	°C
T_{apr}	Average temperature - April	°C
T_{aug}	Average temperature - August	°C
T_{dec}	Average temperature - December	°C
T_{feb}	Average temperature - February	°C
T_{jan}	Average temperature - January	°C
T_{jul}	Average temperature - July	°C
T_{jun}	Average temperature - June	°C
T_{mar}	Average temperature - March	°C
T_{may}	Average temperature - May	°C
T_{nov}	Average temperature - November	°C
T_{oct}	Average temperature - October	°C
T_{sep}	Average temperature - September	°C
V_w	Wind speed	m/s
w	Percentage of time a wind speed occurs during the day	%
z	Surface roughness	m
ρ_{air}^{hub}	Air density at hub	kg/m ³

S-2. Data inputs for simulating wind turbine performance

The model used for simulating the performance data discussed within this paper was compiled and run using MATLAB code developed by the authors. Table S2 below contains the specific inputs used to obtain this report's dataset. Some of the inputs are pre-defined based on the type and location of the wind turbines, while others are set by the authors.

Table S2. List of variables used in the model for simulating wind turbine performance.

Factor	Variable	Value	Reference
Annual project growth rate	G	25%, 30%, 36%	[1]
Area swept by blades	A	45,239 m ²	
Array losses	L_{array}	0%, 5%, 10%	[2]
Auxiliary loads	L_{aux}	5%, 10%	Authors
Average monthly temperatures			[3]
January	T_{jan}	-4.9 °C	
February	T_{feb}	-5.0 °C	
March	T_{mar}	-1.1 °C	
April	T_{apr}	4.0 °C	
May	T_{may}	9.3 °C	
June	T_{jun}	14.4 °C	
July	T_{jul}	17.9 °C	
August	T_{aug}	18 °C	
September	T_{sep}	14.2 °C	
October	T_{oct}	9.1 °C	
November	T_{nov}	3.9 °C	
December	T_{dec}	-2.2 °C	
Blade radius	R	120 m	[4]
Cut-in speed	C_{in}		[4]
Cut-out speed	C_{out}		[4]
Hub height	h_{hub}	150 m	[4]
Natural gas consumption			[5]
Number of starting turbines	$TN_i(i = 1)$	1, 5	Authors

Factor	Variable	Value	Reference
Start year	i_{start}	2025	Authors
Surface roughness	z	0.005 m	[6]
Total summer climate losses	L_s	0.0559 GWh / (Installed MW)	[7]
Total turbines	TN_{max}		Authors
Total winter climate losses	L_w	0.2436 GWh / (Installed MW)	[7]
Wind data			[8]

Employing these inputs, the model simulates electrical output from the turbine array, the number of electrolyzers needed, the amount of hydrogen produced, and the amount of liquid or gaseous fuel consumption in the Maritimes that could be substituted for each month from start to end (this is omitted for scenario γ). The simulation is run for 36 cases. Table S3 below lists these 36 cases, each of which is run monthly from the start (2025) to the end year. The end year depends on the scenario and allows the IES to scale up to the size required to achieve its objective. These are run for each of the five scenarios.

Table S3. Model runs represent a range of deployment ambition and technical performance.

Case number	No. of starting turbines	Growth rate (%)	Auxiliary losses (%)	Array losses (%)
1	1	25	5	0
2	1	25	5	5
3	1	25	5	10
4	1	25	10	0
5	1	25	10	5
6	1	25	10	10
7	1	30	5	0
8	1	30	5	5
9	1	30	5	10
10	1	30	10	0
11	1	30	10	5
12	1	30	10	10
13	1	36	5	0
14	1	36	5	5

Case number	No. of starting turbines	Growth rate (%)	Auxiliary losses (%)	Array losses (%)
15	1	36	5	10
16	1	36	10	0
17	1	36	10	5
18	1	36	10	10
19	5	25	5	0
20	5	25	5	5
21	5	25	5	10
22	5	25	10	0
23	5	25	10	5
24	5	25	10	10
25	5	30	5	0
26	5	30	5	5
27	5	30	5	10
28	5	30	10	0
29	5	30	10	5
30	5	30	10	10
31	5	36	5	0
32	5	36	5	5
33	5	36	5	10
34	5	36	10	0
35	5	36	10	5
36	5	36	10	10

S-3. Model schematics

Table S4. Five scenarios are investigated in this research effort.

Scenario	Description
α	IES meets monthly energy demand served by natural gas. Monthly demand is the most granular data available. U.S. market absorbs excess hydrogen.
β_{tot}	IES meets total annual energy demand served by natural gas. This entails investments in storage and compression capacity.
β_{ind}	IES meets the industrial sector's annual energy demand that is served by natural gas. This entails investments in storage and compression capacity.
γ	IES feeds electricity into the grid through subsea cables. OSW farm sized to replace fossil generation, including sufficient electrolysis and hydrogen storage to provide the grid with two-weeks' worth of OSW output through fuel cells.
δ	IES meets the freight transportation sector's annual demand for hydrogen, but only for freight miles traveled within the region.

Scenario α : Fulfilling monthly gas demand

Scenario β_{tot} : Fulfilling annual gas demand with H₂ storage

Scenario β_{ind} : Fulfilling annual industrial gas demand with H_2 storage

Scenario γ : Employing turbines for electricity production

Figure S1. Schematics outlining how the recursive simulation proceeds in the scenarios under investigation.

S-4. Total number of offshore wind turbines

The total number of offshore wind turbines required to achieve scenario objectives changes depending on the scenario. Each of the five scenarios is run assuming two separate turbine performance profiles, one that simulates maximum (or best) performance and one that simulates minimum (or worst) performance. The maximum performance cases require fewer total turbines due to the higher performance output and vice versa. For scenario α , 388 or 456 turbines are needed to surpass each month's hydrogen demand depending on performance. Scenario β_{tot} requires 310 or 364 to satisfy the annual demand of hydrogen. Scenario β_{ind} requires 209 or 246 turbines to satisfy the annual demand of hydrogen for industry. To replace fossil fueled generation in the Maritimes under the Canada Energy Regulator's "Reference" scenario, scenario γ requires 73 or 86 turbines. Replacing the annual commercial transportation diesel usage in scenario δ requires 12,983 or 15,278 turbines.

S-5. Completion years for each scenario

The table below shows the date range when each scenario could expect to be completed.

Table S5. Range of completion dates for each scenario, including in the cases that begin with 5 starting turbines rather than just 1 starting turbine.

Scenario	Range of completion dates
α	2051 - 2066
β_{tot}	2049 - 2065
β_{ind}	2047 - 2061
γ	2041 - 2052
δ	2070 - 2095

S-6. Wind speed data

The simulated wind speed data used in this investigation come from the National Center for Atmospheric Research's (NCAR) Global Forecast System (GFS) database [8]. Wind speed data are provided at a hub height of 100m, in 6-hour intervals, over the period 2015 to 2020. The wind speed data are for a point on the Scotian shelf—approximately above the Maritimes and Northeast Pipeline (M&NP)—located 44° N and 61° W. We assume that all turbines constituting a wind farm centered on these coordinates would experience similar wind speeds. Using equation (1) below, we extrapolate these wind speeds to wind speeds at a hub height of 150 m, which is the hub height of the International Energy Agency's (IEA) 15MW_e offshore reference turbine that is used in this research:

$$V_w^{hub} = V_w^{100m} \times \frac{\ln\left(\frac{h_{hub}}{z}\right)}{\ln\left(\frac{h_{100m}}{z}\right)} \quad (1)$$

where, V_w^{100m} is the wind speed at 100 m, h_{hub} is the hub height of 150 m, h_{100m} is the height at 100 m, and z is the surface roughness. Since these turbines are located offshore, the surface roughness for open sea is typically 0.0002 m [6]. In this model, it is set to a conservative value of 0.005 m to account for rough waters, islands, and shipping boat traffic. The wind speed data from each month over the 6-year span are then converted into the percentages of wind speeds for an average day of each month. Wind speeds range from 0 to 35 m/s.

S-7. Array power output

The turbine used in this research is the International Energy Agency's (IEA) 15 MWe offshore reference turbine [4] and its hub height, h_{hub} , along with the average monthly temperatures, T_m , in Halifax, Nova Scotia [3] are used to estimate the air density at the hub, ρ_{air}^{hub} . This is done by applying the equations below [9]:

$$T_{air}^{hub} = 15.04 - 0.00649h_{hub} \quad (2)$$

$$P_{air}^{hub} = 101290 \left(\frac{T_{air}^{hub} + 273.15}{288.08} \right)^{5.256} \quad (3)$$

$$\rho_{air}^{hub} = \frac{P_{air}^{hub}}{[286.9(T_{month} - 0.00649 \times h_{hub} + 273.15)]} \quad (4)$$

Equation (2) and Equation (3) calculate the temperature, T_{air}^{hub} , and pressure, P_{air}^{hub} , at the hub height, respectively, assuming that sea level is at standard temperature and pressure conditions [10]. Equation (4) is the ideal gas law formula and takes the average monthly temperatures into account.

The model takes the wind data, the coefficient of performance table (C_p) of the reference turbine, the density of the air, the area swept by the blades, and the auxiliary loads, and uses these to calculate the net turbine electrical production, P_{elec}^{net} . The raw electrical production, P_{elec}^{raw} , of a single turbine is first calculated using Equation (5) below:

$$P_{elec}^{raw} = \sum_{C_{in}}^{C_{out}} C_p \left(\frac{1}{2} \rho_{air}^{hub} \times A \times V_w^{hub3} \right) (w \times 24) \quad (5)$$

where C_{out} is the cut-out speed, C_{in} is the cut-in speed, C_p is the coefficient of performance for the turbine at a specific wind speed, ρ_{air}^{hub} is the density of the air at the hub, A is the area swept by the blades, V_w^{hub} is the velocity of the wind, and w is the percentage of time in a day that a

specific wind speed occurs. The raw power output is reduced by the auxiliary loads and average climate losses for both winter and summer climates [7]. The equations used for calculating the net electrical production of a single turbine, P_{elec}^{net} , for both winter and summer climates respectively are:

$$P_{elec}^{net} = [P_{raw}(1 - L_{aux})] - \frac{(L_w \times 15)}{6} \quad (6)$$

$$P_{elec}^{net} = [P_{raw}(1 - L_{aux})] - \frac{(L_s \times 15)}{6} \quad (7)$$

where L_{aux} is the percentage of auxiliary load the turbine experiences, L_w are the losses associated with winter, and L_s are the losses associated with the summer. The climate losses are evenly split into the 6 months they affect with November to April constituting the winter months and May to October constituting the summer months. To calculate the electrical production of the entire array, P_{elec}^{array} , the following equation is used:

$$P_{elec}^{array} = P_{elec}^{net} \times TN_i(1 - L_{array}) \quad (8)$$

where TN_i is the number of turbines in year i and L_{array} refers to the losses associated with the array arrangement of the turbines. From here, the average monthly power outputs for a single turbine can be estimated by multiplying the P_{elec}^{array} value for a given month by the number of days in that month.

Due to the vast size of the Scotian shelf, it is likely that array losses could be minimized: inter-array distances can be increased to achieve minimal array losses of 0% to 10%, unless other social, economic, and political constraints intrude, which is possible. Constraints most often manifest in concerns regarding other marine interests and aesthetics; our choice of location reduces these. For example, many of the turbines would not be visible from shore.

Ignoring socio-technical constraints, array losses can be minimized by staggering the turbines, specifically by spacing them out parallel to the direction of wind by more than 6.4 times the rotor diameter and spacing them out perpendicular to the direction of the wind by at least 4.3 times the rotor diameter [2].

S-8. Annual project growth rates

To calculate the array electrical production, the value of a single turbine's net power generation in year i is multiplied by the number of turbines in year i . The number of turbines in any given year but the first is determined by the annual project growth rate. The growth rate equation is as follows:

$$TN_{i+1} = (G \times TN_i) \times \left(1 - \frac{TN_i}{TN_{Max}}\right) + TN_i \quad (9)$$

where TN_{i+1} is the number of turbines in year $i + 1$, G is the growth rate, TN_i is the number of turbines for year i , and TN_{max} is the maximum number of turbines for each scenario, in accordance with section S-5.

S-9. Electrolyzers

The electrolyzers used in this research are based on a commercial offering by Siemens, the Silyzer 300, which has a power demand of 17.5 MW and a production rate of 335 kg of hydrogen per hour [11]. We assume the electrolyzers operate at 80% capacity factors. The number of electrolyzers is calculated monthly and depends on the average hourly array electrical production. This assumes that for any given monthly array electrical production, each hour of that month produces the same amount as the next. While this is not ideal, this helps estimate the number of electrolyzers needed to keep up with the array. The required number needed is calculated using the following equation:

$$E = \frac{P_{array}}{d_m \times 24 \times 17.5 \times 0.8} \quad (10)$$

where E is the number of electrolyzers needed per hour on an average day and d_m is the number of days in a particular month, m . This is calculated monthly and the number of electrolyzers needed in any given year is reported based on the month that requires the largest number of electrolyzers to process array power into hydrogen. (This month is usually December.) This ensures sufficient annual electrolysis capacity. The average daily hydrogen output of each of these electrolyzers can then be estimated as follows:

$$P_{H_2}^{kg} = E \times (335 \times 24) \times 0.8 \quad (11)$$

Using the specific volume at standard temperature and pressure [12], the average daily volumetric output of hydrogen can then be calculated:

$$P_{H_2}^{m^3} = P_{H_2}^{kg} \times 11.736 \quad (12)$$

To calculate the volume of hydrogen that would provide the same amount of energy per volume of natural gas or diesel, the ratios of the lower heating values (LHV) are used [13]. For

scenario δ , this is done by taking the LHV of hydrogen and dividing it by the LHV of diesel. The LHV of hydrogen and diesel are 10,224 kJ/m³ and 35,811,696 kJ/m³, respectively so the following equation looks like:

$$D_{supp} = P_{H_2}^{m^3} * \frac{10,224}{35,811,696} \quad (13)$$

For all other scenarios, the LHV ratio of hydrogen to natural gas is used. Due to natural gas having a variety of compositions, the density was assumed to be 0.7 kg/m³, which is typical and fits within the range of densities for natural gas [14] and leads to a LHV of 32,825 kJ/m³.

The equation used is:

$$NG_{supp} = P_{H_2}^{m^3} * \frac{10,224}{32,825} \quad (14)$$

S-10. Estimating avoided emissions

In scenarios α , β_{tot} , and β_{ind} , the emissions avoided by the hydrogen option are found by taking the amount of natural gas that is substituted with hydrogen and multiplying that by the emission factor of natural gas in the Maritimes, which is 1921 gCO₂/m³ NG [15]. The resulting value represents the total amount of CO₂ that would be avoided by substituting natural gas with this hydrogen regardless of when the hydrogen is used (i.e., it might be stored or exported). This is done for each month from the start year to the end year and is reported per year.

In scenario γ , we estimate the annual emissions from fossil fuel generators in the Maritimes up to 2065. We use data from the Canada Energy Regulator's (CER) Reference scenario [16] to compile projections of the amount of electricity that is generated by each source up to 2050. Beyond 2050, we assume that the electricity generation mix remains the same in the absence of further federal projections. The Reference scenario assumes that the share of carbon-intensive electric power generation declines over time, but this decline is not as aggressive as it is in CER's Evolving scenario. The Reference scenario thus represents a hypothetical Canada that does not aggressively pursue its net-zero targets, but muddles through to lower carbon intensities as technology improves and the cost of low-carbon generation falls further.

The goal of the offshore wind farm in scenario γ is to replace the maximum share of electric power generation that comes from fossil fuel resources in the time period under investigation. We consider coal/coke, natural gas, oil, and biomass to be carbon-intensive resources. Each source's emission factor and heat content are taken from both The Climate Registry [17] and Canada's annual Greenhouse Gas Inventory [15], and generator heat rates are extracted from the U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA) and the National Renewable

Energy Laboratory (NREL) [18, 19]. The estimated amount of CO₂ emitted annually from each source, EM_s , is found using the equation below:

$$EM_s = \frac{Elec_s \times \frac{HR_s}{HC_s} \times EF_s}{1000} \quad (15)$$

where $Elec_s$ is the annual amount of electricity generated from that source in a year, HR_s is the generator heat rate, HC_s is the heat content of the fuel, and EF_s is the emission factor for source s . The result corresponds to the maximum amount of emissions that could be avoided from that source in that year. We prioritize the replacement of fossil generators in their expected order of prevalence in 2025, replacing coal first then natural gas, oil, and biomass. The amount of CO₂ avoided, EM_{avoid} , is then calculated using the following equation:

$$EM_{avoid} = \begin{cases} \frac{P_{elec}^{annual} \times \frac{HR_c}{HC_c} \times EF_c}{1000} & \text{if } P_{elec}^{annual} < elec_c \\ \frac{(P_{elec}^{annual} - elec_c) \times \frac{HR_{ng}}{HC_{ng}} \times EF_{ng}}{1000} + EM_c & \text{if } P_{elec}^{annual} < elec_c + elec_{ng} \\ \frac{(P_{elec}^{annual} - elec_c - elec_{ng}) \times \frac{HR_o}{HC_o} \times EF_o}{1000} + EM_c + EM_{ng} & \text{if } P_{elec}^{annual} < elec_c + elec_{ng} + elec_o \\ \frac{(P_{elec}^{annual} - elec_c - elec_{ng} - elec_o) \times \frac{HR_b}{HC_b} \times EF_b}{1000} + EM_c + EM_{ng} + EM_o & \text{if } P_{elec}^{annual} < elec_s^{annual} \\ EM_s^{total} & \text{if } P_{elec}^{annual} \geq elec_s^{annual} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

where P_{elec}^{annual} is the annual amount of electricity produced by the turbine array, EM_s^{total} is the total amount of emissions generated by carbon-intensive sources, $Elec_s^{annual}$ is the annual electricity generated by carbon-intensive sources, and HR , HC , EF , and $elec$ are the heat rate, heat content, emission factor, and generated electricity for coal (c), natural gas (ng), oil (o), and biomass (b). We compare the emissions avoided by our wind farm with the total amount of CO₂ emitted by the Maritimes using data provided by Environment and Climate Change Canada and stretching from 2014 to 2020. The 2019 values for Nova Scotia, New Brunswick, and Prince Edward Island are added to generate estimates of total emissions from the Maritimes, which are

approximately 30 million metric tons of CO₂ [15]. These emissions are expected to decline every year in CER's Reference scenario [16].

For scenario δ , the emission reductions are calculated by converting the amount of generated hydrogen to the diesel equivalent. The amount of diesel that is replaced is then multiplied by the emission factor of diesel, which is 2,680,500 gCO₂/m³ diesel [15].

S-11. Reporting upper and lower bounds

Instead of reporting results for each of the 36 scenarios in the manuscript, we take the best and worst performing cases as indicative of the upper and lower bounds, respectively. Given the centrality of growth rates to our analysis, we report the upper and lower bounds for each of the three different growth rates. This reduces the number of cases to 8 while faithfully summarizing the full range of results.

Table S6. Summary of upper and lower bound scenarios for which results are reported in the manuscript

Number of Starting Turbines	Growth Rate (%)	Auxiliary Losses (%)	Array Losses (%)
1	25	5	0
1	25	10	10
1	36	5	0
1	36	10	10
5	25	5	0
5	25	10	10
5	36	5	0
5	36	10	10

S-12. Cost estimation

Nine categories of costs are considered in this techno-economic analysis, as summarized in Table S7 below. Some costs are relevant only for some scenarios.

Table S7. Nine costs are considered in this techno-economic analysis

Cost group	Cost	Relevant scenarios	Reference
Turbine costs	CAPEX	$\alpha, \beta_{tot}, \beta_{ind}, \gamma, \delta$	[20]
	FO&M	$\alpha, \beta_{tot}, \beta_{ind}, \gamma, \delta$	
Electrolyzer costs	CAPEX	$\alpha, \beta_{tot}, \beta_{ind}, \gamma, \delta$	[21, 22, 23]
	FO&M	$\alpha, \beta_{tot}, \beta_{ind}, \gamma, \delta$	
Storage costs	Compressor CAPEX	$\beta_{tot}, \beta_{ind}, \gamma, \delta$	[24]
	Conditioning	$\beta_{tot}, \beta_{ind}, \gamma, \delta$	
	Cavern storage CAPEX	$\beta_{tot}, \beta_{ind}, \gamma, \delta$	
Social cost of carbon		$\alpha, \beta_{tot}, \beta_{ind}, \gamma, \delta$	[25]
Discount rate		$\alpha, \beta_{tot}, \beta_{ind}, \gamma, \delta$	[26]

This model incorporates declining prices for the turbines and electrolyzers to account for technological learning, also known as learning economies. Storage costs remain the same regardless of year: the storage cavern comprises a one-time purchase, though storage might first become necessary at different years in different scenarios. The social cost of carbon is taken to be a step-function, increasing every 5 years. The values of the step function are taken from [27].

These costs all have a lower, middle, and upper value, except for storage costs. In addition, both project growth rate and turbine performance could take a lower, middle, or upper value. The number of starting turbines can only be changed between its low and high value. These changes introduce many different possible scenarios that affect the total cost, cost of H₂, cost of CO₂ abatement, and total emission reductions. The values listed in Table S8 below are the range of values for the first year as some values change as the years progress.

Table S8. Cost estimates used in this analysis

Cost	Unit	Lower	Middle	Upper	Reference
Annual project growth rate		25%	30%	36%	[1]
Turbine performance	GWh	71.5		75.7	Model
Turbine CAPEX ^a	USD/kW	\$3172.54	\$3774.80	\$5459.65	[20]
Turbine FO&M ^a	USD/kWyr	\$58.26	\$68.40	\$95.28	
Electrolyzer CAPEX ^a	USD/kW	\$500	\$2000	\$6500	[21, 22, 23]
Electrolyzer FO&M ^a	USD/kWyr	\$14.25	\$57	\$360	[21, 22, 23]
Discount rate	%	3	5	7	[26]
Turbine lifetime	Year	20	25	30	[28, 29]
Electrolyzer lifetime	Year	5	10	15	[11]
Compressor efficiency	kWh/kgH ₂	1.6	4.4	18	[30]
PEM fuel cell efficiency	%	50	60	70	[31]

^a Starting cost in 2025

The turbine costs are in 2018 USD with inflation considered by the authors. The turbine costs decrease every year per the 2020 Annual Technology Baseline (ATB) estimates from the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) [20].

For this study, we take the costs of offshore wind turbines class 8 through 12 as representative of the type of systems that would be deployed in the Scotian Shelf, given its water depths. The lower bound costs come from the class 8 advanced estimates, the middle costs are from the class 10 moderate estimates, and the upper bound cost come from class 12 conservative estimates.

We develop annual estimates for capital expenditure (CAPEX) and Fixed Operation and Maintenance (FO&M). CAPEX costs include offshore wind overnight capital costs (OCC), construction financing, and grid connection costs. While it may seem unnecessary to include grid connection costs in scenarios all scenarios except for γ , this large array will need auxiliary power, most likely from the bulk grid, to maintain system health during periods of no wind. Grid connection costs could be associated with running an undersea cable to shore, or with providing some form of on-site power if that is deemed feasible and preferable. Grid connection costs are smaller than OCC, but they are significant (between ~28% and ~40% of OCC, depending on turbine class).

The same cost evolution seen in offshore wind was then implemented on a database of (widely varying) electrolyzer costs [21, 23]. The two technologies sit at a similar technological readiness level: they are technologically ready, commercially available, but not widely deployed yet. While the supply chain has not scaled up to the level that would enable radical deployment, they remain somewhat modular technologies relative to nuclear power or carbon capture technologies. There is evidence that modular technologies experience faster learning rates than non-modular systems [32].

Storage costs are held static due to uncertainty regarding how the cost of building storage caverns might change over time. The few data we found on storage costs are dated. Storage costs are split into three groups: compressor capital costs, conditioning, and cavern capital costs. Compressor capital costs deal with the initial capital cost of the compressors needed for the storage system: we take these to be ~\$1,300/kW. Conditioning costs refer to the costs associated with compressing and cooling the hydrogen and are taken to be ~\$0.02/kgH₂. Cavern capital costs refer to the cost of building the physical underground cavern required to store hydrogen, as

well as the balance of the storage system, apart from compression and conditioning. These costs are taken to be approximately \$9/kgH₂. For scenarios β_{ind} and δ , the rates of hydrogen generated is significantly higher, so the costs are adjusted accordingly. For β_{ind} , the compressor costs and conditioning costs are ~\$800/kW and ~\$0.01/kgH₂, respectively. For δ , the compressor costs and conditioning costs are ~\$500/kW and ~\$0.01/kgH₂, respectively. All these values assume a rate of hydrogen production of the same order of magnitude as that in our scenarios, as outlined in [24].

S-13. Retirements and replacement

In the recursive simulation, turbines and electrolyzers are replaced once they reach the end of their useful lives. We take 25 years to be our best estimate of the lifetime of an offshore wind turbine; for the electrolyzers, this estimate is 10 years (~100,000 hours). Lower and upper bounds are developed for both, assuming that the lifetime of both turbines and electrolyzers could be extended or shortened by 5 years. When calculating costs, we consider both the addition of new turbines to meet the stipulated growth rate and the number of replacements needed to replace retired assets.

S-14. Hydrogen storage

For the four cases that involve hydrogen storage, scenarios β_{tot} , β_{ind} , γ , and δ , an underground cavern storage system is employed. The overall cost of this system is split into three separate costs: compressor capital costs, compression costs, and cavern capital costs. In scenarios β_{tot} and β_{ind} , the amount of hydrogen storage is determined by finding the excess of hydrogen produced each year after project completion. The purchase of storage does not actually occur on this year, but on the first year where there is a month that produces excess hydrogen. In scenarios γ and δ , the hydrogen storage is purchased at the beginning of the project. In both cases, storage cost is static due to uncertainty regarding how the cost of building storage caverns might change over time.

The calculation of storage cavern capacity is different in each scenario. The storage capacity is estimated by calculating the minimum amount required to meet annual demand and adding the amount needed for two-weeks' worth of storage. The two-weeks' worth of storage is also different for each of the scenarios. The table below lists each of the scenarios and their required storage size.

Table S9. Storage size requirements for each scenario

Scenario	Two-weeks of storage (Tonnes)	Total storage (Tonnes)
α	0	0
β_{tot}	12,100	22,300
β_{ind}	9,100	27,800-28,000 ^a
γ	6,400 - 9,000 ^b	6,400 - 9,000 ^b
δ	695,000	695,000

^a Depends on turbine performance.

^b Depends on fuel cell efficiency. Efficiencies used range from 50-70%

The additional storage constitutes an effort to build resilience into this system, helping address unaccounted downtime for up to two weeks (e.g., due to a wind drought). This value is also rounded up to the nearest 100 tH₂ to ensure there is adequate storage capacity. The cost of storage is calculated using (now admittedly dated) cost estimates provided by Amos at NREL [24].

In scenario γ , storage capacity is sized to accommodate sufficient hydrogen to meet two-weeks' worth of OSW output. Again, this is intended to provide some measure of resource adequacy and resilience in case of extended wind droughts. For context, the longest wind drought in the Scotian Shelf data we collected from NCAR lasted approximately 5 days. 6,400 to 9,000 metric tons of hydrogen storage are needed, depending on fuel cell efficiency. This number is also rounded up to the nearest 100 tH₂ to be conservative.

S-15. Uncertainty analysis

To determine the uncertainty of project or production costs to the various cost components under investigation, a Monte Carlo simulation is performed using Palisade's @Risk software version 8.2 [33]. The Monte Carlo simulations were each run with 10,000 samples and cumulative ascending distributions were created for each of the following results: total real project costs; hydrogen (or electricity) costs in 2025; and hydrogen (or electricity) costs at project completion. This simulation varied all the variables listed above in Table S8. Below are all three distributions for each scenario.

Figure S2. Scenario α cumulative distributions of the **A)** total real cost of the project, **B)** hydrogen production costs in 2025 (the initial year in the simulation), and **C)** hydrogen production costs at project completion.

Figure S3. Scenario β_{tot} cumulative distributions of the **A)** total real cost of the project, **B)** hydrogen production costs in 2025 (the initial year in the simulation), and **C)** hydrogen production costs at project completion.

Figure S4. Scenario β_{ind} cumulative distributions of the **A)** total real cost of the project, **B)** hydrogen production costs in 2025 (the initial year in the simulation), and **C)** hydrogen production costs at project completion.

Figure S5. Scenario γ cumulative distributions of the **A)** total real cost of the project, **B)** electric power production costs in 2025 (the initial year in the simulation), and **C)** the electric power production costs at project completion.

Figure S6. Scenario δ cumulative distributions of the **A)** total real cost of the project, **B)** hydrogen production costs in 2025 (the initial year in the simulation), and **C)** hydrogen production costs at project completion.

S-16. Monthly capacity factors

To assess monthly variations in the utilization of system components, monthly capacity factors are calculated for both turbine and electrolyzer arrays using the following two equations, respectively.

$$CF_t = \frac{P_{elec}^{array}}{\left(\frac{TN_i * 15 * 24 * d_m}{10^6} \right)} \quad (17)$$

$$CF_e = \frac{\left(\frac{P_{H_2}^{kg}}{24} \right)}{335 * NE_i} \quad (18)$$

S-17. Natural gas consumption in the Maritimes

The natural gas consumption data for α , β_{tot} , and β_{ind} were obtained from Statistics Canada [34]. Consumption data from January 2016 to December 2021 was collected for Nova Scotia and New Brunswick (PEI is excluded since there is no natural gas consumption). These monthly datasets include a breakdown of industrial, commercial, and residential use. Exploratory data analysis showed wide variation between the Statistics Canada data and the data compiled by the Canada Energy Regulator (CER). Personal communication with the former helped the research team isolate line items in Statistics Canada's databases that, when summed, generate an estimate of natural gas consumption that is close to CER's data.

In order to estimate 2050 loads, the annual consumption of 2016 to 2021 was plotted and a linear trend was developed to forecast 2050 annual consumption. 2050 monthly values were also estimated by creating an average percentage distribution of the consumptions for each month within a year. Every year after 2050 is assumed to have the same consumption. In scenario α , the system is overbuilt so that even in the worst case, the minimum hydrogen production exceeds the estimated monthly demand. In scenarios β_{tot} and β_{ind} , where storage is utilized, there is no need for the turbine array to be overbuilt because storage exists to satisfy demand. An additional two-weeks' worth of storage is added to these values and would enhance the resilience of the system (or help account for decreases in wind power production or increases in energy demand). Scenarios γ and δ include these safety factors within their storage components. Enough hydrogen is stored to account for two-weeks' worth of electrical or diesel demand. Like the previous scenario, this could help absorb changes in the supply and demand.

S-18. Natural gas pipeline

The presence and coordinates of the Maritimes and Northeast Pipeline (M&NP) dictated our choice of case study location. Having access to a large, relatively new, bidirectional pipeline that extends throughout the Maritimes—from Maine to the Sable Island Bank 200km offshore—means that the current infrastructure to transport gas across the Maritimes already exists as well as the ability to contain the amount of hydrogen produced [35]. While many natural gas distribution pipelines in the Maritimes are made of hydrogen-compatible materials, extensive testing and modification might be required to ensure that hydrogen can be carried safely in these pipelines [36]. The pipeline integrity question is reserved for future work.

S-19. Results from the case with 5 starting turbines

While the manuscript focuses on elaborating the results of cases with 1 starting turbine, results from cases with 5 starting turbines can be found in the tables below.

Table S10. Cost ranges for hydrogen production scenarios with 5 starting turbines

Scenario	Completion year	Starting H ₂ cost (\$/kg H ₂)	Completion H ₂ cost (\$/kg H ₂)	Total emission reduction (million tonnes)
α	2051 – 2062	36 – 122	1.3 – 18.0	55.1 – 78.2
β_{tot}	2049 – 2061	36 – 122	1.4 – 18.5	40.2 – 62.8
β_{ind}	2047 – 2057	36 – 122	1.6 – 18.9	25.8 – 37.9
δ	2070 – 2090	834 – 1,230	0.8 – 15.3	3,600 – 5,500

Table S11. Cost ranges for scenario γ with 5 starting turbines

Scenario	Completion Year	Starting electricity cost (\$/kWh)	Completion electricity cost (\$/kWh)	Total emission reduction (million tonnes)
γ	2041 – 2048	0.8 – 3.0	0.04 – 0.20	42.0 – 53.7

S-20. Scenario δ – Transportation calculations

Scenario δ , which replaces the diesel usage in the Maritimes with hydrogen, is calculated by summing up the total vehicle miles traveled in the Maritimes by freight trucks. The Canadian Freight Analysis Framework (CFAF) from Statistics Canada [37] contains data from 2011 to 2017 containing the number of shipments, total distance traveled, shipment values, etc. for various pairs of routes to, from, and across Canada. For simplicity, it is assumed that the distance per each trip for any route can be found by taking the total distance traveled and dividing it by the number of shipments for that route. The yearly datasets are used to estimate the amount of diesel required for the 2050 target date with a linear trend.

Only the routes that included one of the Maritime’s provinces as either an origin or destination were considered. Not every exact origin or destination is listed—some are grouped under a provincial label (e.g., “Rest of Nova Scotia”, rather than “Halifax” or “Truro”). For these locations, cities that lead to a distance error of less than 5% (when compared to the distance per trip) were selected. It was also assumed that any routes that had either origin or destination as the same two cities traveled along the same route, but in different directions (e.g., freight from “Halifax to Montreal” is assumed to travel along the same route as freight from “Montreal to Halifax”). Table S12 below shows all the cities selected to replace “provincially labeled” Canadian locations.

Table S12. Locations selected to replace “provincially labeled” Canadian locations

Original Location Label	New Location
New Brunswick, NB	Priceville, NB
Newfoundland and Labrador, NL	St. Johns, NL
Northwest Territories, NT	Whati, NT
Prince Edward Island, PE	Oyster Bed Bridge, PE

Original Location Label	New Location
Rest of Alberta, AB	Slave Lake, AB
Rest of British Columbia, BC	Sunnyside, BC
Rest of Manitoba, MB	Brandon, MB
Rest of Nova Scotia, NS	Stewiacke, NS
Rest of Ontario, ON	Peterborough, ON
Rest of Quebec, QC	Trois-Rivières, QC
Rest of Saskatchewan, SK	Waskesiu Lake, SK
Yukon Territories, YT	Mayo, YT

The only location not listed in the table above is Nunavut, Nunavut. This was not included because it is assumed that the total distance driven for these routes is within the Maritimes, with the actual trip from the border to Nunavut requiring either air or sea shipment. The new locations chosen in Table S12 sometimes had to be modified to reduce the error between our analysis and CFAF data to <5%. Table S13 lists these exceptions.

Table S13. Routes selected to replace specific Canadian domestic routes

Original Route	New Route
Whati, NT → Oyster Bed Bridge, PE	Wrigley, NT → Oyster Bed Bridge, PE
Trois-Rivières, QC → Priceville, NB	Beauceville, QC → Priceville, NB
Montreal, QC → Priceville, NB	Montreal, QC → Neguac, NB
Whati, NT → Priceville, NB	Whati, NT → Moncton, NB
Peterborough, ON → Priceville, NB	Peterborough, ON → Moncton, NB
Toronto, ON → Priceville, NB	Toronto, ON → Moncton, NB
Edmonton, AB → Stewiacke, NS	Edmonton, AB → Sherbrooke, NS
Montreal, QC → Stewiacke, NS	Montreal, QC → Sherbrooke, NS
Whati, NT → Stewiacke, NS	Whati, NT → Cape North, NS
Oshawa, ON → Stewiacke, NS	Oshawa, ON → Sherbrooke, NS
Quebec City, QC → Stewiacke, NS	Quebec City, QC → Antigonish, NS
Peterborough, ON → Stewiacke, NS	Peterborough, ON → Sherbrooke, NS
Trois-Rivières, QC → Stewiacke, NS	Trois-Rivières, QC → Sherbrooke, NS

Original Route	New Route
Winnipeg, MB → Stewiacke, NS	Winnipeg, MB → Sydney, NS
Peterborough, ON → Oyster Bed Bridge, PE	Peterborough, ON → Elmira, PE
Trois-Rivières, QC → Oyster Bed Bridge, PE	Trois-Rivières, QC → North Wiltshire, PE
St. Johns, NL → Halifax, NS	Whitebourne, NL → Halifax, NS
St. Johns, NL → Priceville, NB	Clarenville, NL → Priceville, NB
St. Johns, NL → Oyster Bed Bridge, NB	Clarenville, NL → Oyster Bed Bridge, NB

Moreover, some of the routes were international and included origins or destinations within the United States or Mexico. We assume all such shipments travel to the United States, since the amount of trade with the United States (~\$900 billion in 2020) is significantly higher than that with Mexico (~\$28 billion in 2020) [38]. International routes were plotted as a histogram and split into six bins depending on the length of the shipment’s route, as reported in CFAF. This can be seen in Figure S7 below.

Figure S7 - Histogram of international routes split into 1000 km bins

Table S14 shows the specific city locations used to represent each of the route bins shown in Figure S7.

Table S14. United States locations based on distance

Distance (km)	Location
[256 – 1,256]	Springfield, MA
(1,256 – 2,256]	Columbus, OH
(2,256 – 3,256]	Bloomfield, IL
(3,256 – 4,256]	Houston, TX
(4,256 – 5,256]	Pheonix, AZ
(5,256 – 6,256]	San Diego, CA

Like the domestic Canadian routes, the international routes also have exceptions. Table S15 below lists these exceptions, which were employed to reduce the error between our results and CFAF data to <5%.

Table S15. Routes selected to replace specific international routes

Original Route	New Route
Springfield, MA → Oyster Bed Bridge, PE	Albany, NY → Oyster Bed Bridge, PE
Springfield, MA → Priceville, NB	New Haven, CT → Priceville, NB
Columbus, OH → Oyster Bed Bridge, PE	Cleveland, OH → Oyster Bed Bridge, PE
Bloomfield, IL → Priceville, NB	Miami, FL → Priceville, NB
Bloomfield, IL → Oyster Bed Bridge, PE	Columbia, MO → Oyster Bed Bridge, PE
Houston, TX → Priceville, NB	Albuquerque, NM → Priceville, NB
San Diego, CA → Halifax, NS	Pheonix, AZ → Halifax, NS

All two-city pairings were input into Google Maps, and the distance traveled within the Maritimes was measured starting from the port of entry (i.e., the border of the three provinces that constitute the Maritimes) to the intended destination. Google Maps alters routes due to traffic conditions, so it is important to note that the above route distances were all estimated during the time period from March 22 to 24, 2022. The following equation was repeated for each

unique route to determine the percentage of distance driven in the Maritimes for each year from 2011 to 2017.

$$MP_r = \frac{MD_r}{TD_r} \quad (19)$$

where MP_r is the percentage driven in the Maritimes for each route, r , MD_r is the distance traveled in the Maritimes for each route, and TD_r is the total distance traveled for each route.

These percentages are then applied to each route and the total distance traveled within the Maritimes is calculated each year with:

$$D_y = \sum_r MP_r * NS_{r,y} \quad (20)$$

where D_y is the distance traveled in the Maritimes for each year, y and $NS_{r,y}$ is the number of shipments for each route in each year. These yearly distances are multiplied by the fuel efficiency of a semi truck. The U.S. Department on Energy states the fuel efficiency of this type of truck is 5.29 miles per gasoline gallon equivalent [39]. Converting this to its diesel equivalency returns 5.9 MPG [13] which is what is used to calculate the total gallons of diesel consumed for that year. Gallons are then converted to cubic meters and then each year is plotted. Using the estimated values from 2050, it is determined that the amount of diesel needed is about 60.7 million cubic meters or about 213 billion cubic meters of hydrogen which is calculated as follows:

$$H_{Supp} = D_{2050} * \frac{35,811,696}{10,224} \quad (21)$$

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